

Synthesis and characterization of some 3-*N*-alkoxyphthalimido-5-arylidene-2- $\{[4-(4\text{-substituted phenyl})-1,3\text{-thiazol-2-yl}]imino\}$ -1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones

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Abstract : 4-Chloro/methyl phenacyl bromide **1a-b** reacted with thiourea to furnish 2-amino thiazole **2a-b** through Hantzsch's process, which were converted to their thiazolidinone derivatives **4a-b**, by the reaction of corresponding thiazolyl thiourea **3a-b** with chloroacetic acid in the presence of sodium acetate. Subsequent treatment of **4a-b** with aromatic aldehydes **5a-c**, followed by condensation with ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides **7a-b** afforded titled compounds **8a-l**.

Keywords : 2-Amino thiazole, thiourea, phenacyl bromide, condensation, ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimide.

Introduction

Among a wide variety of heterocycles that have been explored for developing pharmaceutically important molecules, thiazoles, thiazolidinones and related compounds have played an important role in medicinal chemistry. 2-Amino thiazole derivatives acquire a special place in the heterocyclic field because of their diversified activities, such as antimicrobial, antitubercular¹ and anti-inflammatory. Thiazoles are common structural element in many natural products like Vit-B₁, tubulysene, thioestrepton, which are vastly used in antiviral², antiallergic and antihelmintic activities. Antitumor^{3,4} activity is shown especially when this moiety attached to phenyl ring. Important pharmacological activities shown by amino-oxy and imidoxy derivatives such as anticancer⁵, antimalarial⁶, anticonvulsant⁷ etc. prompted a great interest in the synthesis of some alpha hydroxylamine derivatives containing thia-zole moiety^{8,9}. In the light of these observations, an effort has been made to synthesize such combinational molecules that possess all above biologically active moieties together.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation biologically active 5-benzylidene-3-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-2- $\{[4\text{-methylphenyl}]$ -1,3-thiazol-2-yl $\}imino\}$ -1,3-thiazolidin-4-one **8a** was synthesized by a series of reactions. 2-Aminothiazole **2a** was

prepared from reaction of 4-methyl phenacyl bromide **1a** with thiourea in ethanol. Treatment of **2a** with ammonium thiocyanate in HCl followed by cyclization with chloroacetic acid in ethanol and in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate yielded **3a** and **4a** respectively. Structures of these compounds were established on the basis of IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. The intense band at 1695 cm⁻¹ for C=O str. and 3398 cm⁻¹ of NH str., as well as a singlet of N-H proton at δ 9.2 confirmed the formation of **4a**, which was further treated with benzaldehyde **5a** in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid, **6a** was obtained in quantitative yield, in which C=O str. appears at 1686 cm⁻¹ due to conjugation. Titled compound **8a** was obtained from the condensation of **6a** with ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide **7a** in absolute alcohol, using pyridine as a base, characterized by disappearance of NH str. at 3390 and N-H singlet at δ 9.12 which were present in its precursor and appearance of new C-O and N-O str. band at 1180 and 1370 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Physical and analytical data of all the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points of all the synthesized compounds were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 (FTIR) spectrometer and ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO) were

Note

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of compounds 2a-b, 3a-b, 4a-b, 6a-f and 8a-l

Compd.	R	R ₁	n	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
								C	N
2a	CH ₃	-	-	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	190	80	135	63.12 (63.15)	14.69 (14.73)
2b	Cl	-	-	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ SCl	210.5	72	118	51.25 (51.30)	13.23 (13.30)
3a	CH ₃	-	-	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	249	66	290	52.90 (53.01)	16.78 (16.86)
3b	Cl	-	-	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	269	65	> 300	44.45 (44.52)	15.54 (15.58)
4a	CH ₃	-	-	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂	289	54	299	53.89 (53.97)	14.49 (14.53)
4b	Cl	-	-	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl	309	65	295	46.44 (46.52)	13.51 (13.57)

Table-1 (contd.)

6a	CH ₃	H	-	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	377	42	250	63.61 (63.66)	11.11 (11.14)
6b	CH ₃	Cl	-	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl	411	68	283	58.26 (58.32)	10.16 (10.20)
6c	CH ₃	OCH ₃	-	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	407	47	290	61.82 (61.91)	10.27 (10.31)
6d	Cl	H	-	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl	397	54	244	57.24 (57.35)	10.49 (10.56)
6e	Cl	Cl	-	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl ₂	432	52	298	52.70 (52.77)	9.68 (9.72)
6f	Cl	OCH ₃	-	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	427	47	273	56.11 (56.14)	9.78 (9.82)
8a	CH ₃	H	2	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	566	55	282	63.54 (63.60)	9.86 (9.89)
8b	CH ₃	H	4	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	594	65	293	64.57 (64.64)	9.38 (9.42)
8c	CH ₃	Cl	2	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	600	47	247	59.89 (59.95)	9.25 (9.32)
8d	CH ₃	Cl	4	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	628	48	225	61.01 (61.09)	8.89 (8.91)
8e	CH ₃	OCH ₃	2	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂ Cl	596	40	190	62.35 (62.41)	9.34 (9.39)
8f	CH ₃	OCH ₃	4	C ₃₃ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂ Cl	624	55	207	63.39 (63.46)	8.93 (8.97)
8g	Cl	H	2	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	586	58	> 300	59.31 (59.33)	9.49 (9.54)
8h	Cl	H	4	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	614	59	230	60.49 (60.53)	9.08 (9.11)
8i	Cl	Cl	2	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂	620	43	288	56.00 (56.03)	8.97 (9.01)
8j	Cl	Cl	4	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂	648	48	> 300	57.26 (57.31)	8.58 (8.62)
8k	Cl	OCH ₃	2	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂ Cl	616	62	297	58.33 (58.39)	9.01 (9.08)
8l	Cl	OCH ₃	4	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂ Cl	644	47	283	59.55 (59.58)	8.62 (8.68)

recorded on a DRX-300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The ESI-MS spectra were recorded on a MICROMASS QUATTRO II triple quadrupole mass spectrometer having a JASCO PU-980 HPLC pump connected to it. The purity of synthesized compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G plates as adsorbent and ethyl acetate as eluent. Spots were exposed in iodine vapour. All compounds gave satisfactory micro

analytical results. In present investigation, the compounds ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides¹⁰ **7a-b** and 4-substituted phenacyl bromide¹¹ **1a-b** were prepared by the reported methods.

Synthesis of 4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine [Hantzsch's procedure] (2a): To a solution of 4-methyl phenacyl bromide **1a** (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml), thiourea (0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for 2 h.

After cooling, solid obtained was washed with water, dried and crystallized from alcohol. Compound **2b** was also prepared by similar method with minor modifications.

Synthesis of 1-[4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]-thiourea (3a): Compound **2a** (0.01 mol) dissolved in warm 1 N HCl and ammonium thiocyanate (0.02 mol) was added to the solution and refluxed for 6 h. After cooling the product separated was collected by filtration and recrystallized from DMF. Similarly **3b** was prepared by changing concentration of HCl and reflux time.

Synthesis of 2-[[4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (4a): A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol), monochloro acetic acid (0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.02 mol) in absolute alcohol was refluxed for 10–12 h. It was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting precipitate was filtered, recrystallised from DMF. Compound **4b** was prepared by minor modification in reaction condition.

4a: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3398 (N–H str.), 3038 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2940 (C–H str., CH₃), 2829 (C–H str., CH₂), 1695 (C=O str.), 1594 (C=N str.), 670 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 9.2 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–7.2 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.89 (1H, s, SCH), 4.4 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of 5-benzylidene-2-[[4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (6a): A mixture of benzaldehyde **5a** (0.01 mol), thiazolidinone **4a** (0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.02 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 14–16 h. After cooling, the solution was poured into ice-cold water and kept overnight. The resulting product was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF. Compounds **6b–f** were also synthesized by the similar method using appropriate reactants with required change in reflux time.

6a: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3390 (N–H str.), 3025 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2938 (C–H str., CH₃), 1686 (C=O str.), 1592 (C=N str.), 685 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 9.12 (1H, s, NH), 7.4–7.2 (9H, m, Ar–H), 6.93 (1H, s, SCH), 6.34 (1H, s, =CHAr), 2.21 (3H, s, CH₃).

6c: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3384 (N–H str.), 3020 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2942 (C–H str., CH₃), 1683 (C=O str.), 1586 (C=N str.), 682 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 9.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–7.2 (8H, m, Ar–H), 6.92 (1H, s, SCH), 6.3 (1H, s, =CHAr), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of 5-benzylidene-3-N-ethoxyphthalimido-2-

[[4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (8a) :

A mixture of compound **6a** (0.01 mol), ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide **7a** (0.01 mol), pyridine (0.02 mol) in absolute alcohol was refluxed for 18 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and excess of the solvent from the filtrate was removed under reduced pressure. On cooling, the solid separated was crystallized from DMF. Compounds **8a–l** were also synthesized by the minor modifications in reaction condition.

8a: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3030 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2929 (C–H str., CH₃), 2830 (C–H str., CH₂), 1758, 1709 (C=O str.), 1594 (C=N str.), 1370 (N–O str.), 1180 (C–O str.), 695 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 7.95–7.35 (13H, m, Ar–H), 7.2 (1H, s, SCH), 6.3 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.6 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.83 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃); m/z 566 [M]⁺, 514, 464, 433, 409, 393, 377, 365, 338, 205, 190.

8b: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3016 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2984 (C–H str., CH₃), 2865 (C–H str., CH₂), 1750, 1723 (C=O str.), 1601 (C=N str.), 1376 (N–O str.), 1195 (C–O str.), 665 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 7.94–7.38 (13H, m, Ar–H), 7.01 (1H, s, SCH), 6.25 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.6 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.83 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃) 1.85 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); m/z 594 [M]⁺, 534, 489, 487, 412, 399, 365, 349, 216, 190.

8c: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3048 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2941 (C–H str., CH₃), 2834 (C–H str., CH₂), 1760, 1718 (C=O str.), 1601 (C=N str.), 1379 (N–O str.), 1185 (C–O str.), 699 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 7.8–7.5 (12H, m, Ar–H), 7.23 (1H, s, SCH), 6.4 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.62 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.86 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.52 (3H, s, CH₃); m/z 600 [M]⁺, 602, [M+2]⁺, 509, 476, 424, 400, 368, 196, 162, 138, 73.

8d: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3051 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2959 (C–H str., CH₃), 2812 (C–H str., CH₂), 1775, 1720 (C=O str.), 1597 (C=N str.), 1385 (N–O str.), 1174 (C–O str.), 746 (C–Cl str.), 715 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 7.8–7.6 (12H, m, Ar–H), 7.22 (1H, s, SCH), 6.41 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.63 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.81 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.52 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.90 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); m/z 628 [M]⁺, 630, [M+2]⁺, 525, 487, 454, 412, 374, 196, 162, 138, 85.

8e: ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3026 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2938 (C–H str., CH₃), 2825 (C–H str., CH₂), 1751, 1708 (C=O str.), 1590 (C=N str.), 1176 (C–O str.), 693 (C–S–C str.); δ (DMSO) : 7.68–7.46 (12H, m, Ar–H), 7.18 (1H,

s, SCH), 6.25 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.58 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.82 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.65 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃); *m/z* 596 [M]⁺, 514, 492, 450, 436, 422, 392, 190, 148, 132.

8f: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3059 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2949 (C-H str., CH₂), 2836 (C-H str., CH₂), 1768, 1712 (C=O str.), 1602 (C=N str.), 1378 (N-O str.), 1185 (C-O str.), 692 (C-S-C str.); δ (DMSO): 7.64–7.48 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.20 (1H, s, SCH), 6.31 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.57 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.80 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃) 1.95 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); *m/z* 624 [M]⁺, 436, 218, 188, 174, 142, 120.

8g: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3050 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2836 (C-H str., CH₂), 1759, 1712 (C=O str.), 1599 (C=N str.), 1370 (N-O str.), 1182 (C-O str.), 695 (C-S-C str.); δ (DMSO): 7.85–7.4 (13H, m, Ar-H), 7.3 (1H, s, SCH), 6.31 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.60 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.85 (2H, t, NCH₂); *m/z* 586 [M]⁺, 588 [M+2]⁺, 500, 452, 449, 424, 378, 176, 136, 73.

8h: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3045 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2980 (C-H str., CH₂), 1751, 1716 (C=O str.), 1611 (C=N str.), 1358 (N-O str.), 1146 (C-O str.); δ (DMSO): 7.8–7.2 (13H, m, Ar-H), 7.3 (1H, s, SCH), 6.32 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.69 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.75 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.20 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); *m/z* 614 [M]⁺, 616 [M+2]⁺, 396, 218, 111, 90, 83.

8i: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3070 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2846 (C-H str., CH₂), 1789, 1728 (C=O str.), 1604 (C=N str.), 1372 (N-O str.), 1184 (C-O str.), 761 (C-Cl str.); δ (DMSO): 8.1–7.62 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.34 (1H, s, SCH), 6.37 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.63 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.89 (2H, t, NCH₂); *m/z* 620 [M]⁺, 624 [M+4]⁺, 516, 497, 484, 424, 388, 208, 190, 168, 86.

8j: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3061 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2890 (C-H str., CH₂), 1775, 1723 (C=O str.), 1615 (C=N str.), 1354 (N-O str.), 1167 (C-O str.), 765 (C-Cl str.); δ (DMSO): 8.12–7.63 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.37 (1H, s, SCH), 6.41 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.63 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.79 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.08 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); *m/z* 648 [M]⁺, 652 [M+4]⁺, 440, 218, 124, 111, 83.

8k: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3056 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2941 (C-H

str., CH₃), 1762, 1712 (C=O str.), 1599 (C=N str.), 1368 (N-O str.), 1179 (C-O str.), 753 (C-Cl str.), 698 (C-S-C str.); δ (DMSO): 7.8–7.34 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.29 (1H, s, SCH), 6.25 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.58 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.83 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH₃); *m/z* 616 [M]⁺, 618 [M+2]⁺, 530, 484, 470, 424, 384, 220, 190, 136, 69.

8l: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3043 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2965 (C-H str., CH₃), 1751, 1726 (C=O str.), 1605 (C=N str.), 1354 (N-O str.), 1139 (C-O str.), 742 (C-Cl str.), 703 (C-S-C str.); δ (DMSO): 7.81–7.38 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.29 (1H, s, SCH), 6.19 (1H, s, =CHAr), 4.49 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.85 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.4 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.95 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂); *m/z* 644 [M]⁺, 646 [M+2]⁺, 512, 432, 452, 408, 323, 212, 190, 121, 58.

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References

1. A. K. Manian, G. G. Khadse and S. R. Sengupta, *Indian Drngs*, 1993, **30**, 324.
2. V. S. Jolly and K. P. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 412.
3. I. Hutchinson, S. A. Jennings, B. R. Vishnuvajjala, A. D. Westwell and M. F. G. Stevens, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 744.
4. L. Racene, R. Stojkovic, V. Tralic-Kulenovic and G. Karminski-Zamola, *Molecules*, 2006, **11**, 325.
5. G. A. Rosenthal and D. L. Dahlman, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1990, **265**, 868.
6. B. J. Burger, *Antimicrob. Agents and Chemotherapy*, 2000, **14**, 2540.
7. W. G. Loscher, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, **1**, 1342.
8. D. Mehta and G. L. Talesara, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2000, **12**, 14.
9. L. Bauer and K. S. Suresh, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1604.
10. Rather and Reid, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 77.